

The author names were used to plot a network visualization map. This map was created with the computer program VOSviewer, version 1.6.20 (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). This map shows the network of co-authorships links of publications on Brassicaceae, with at least 10 documents and 1 connection, resulting in showing 124 authors. For layout parameters, attraction is set to 1 and repulsion to -2.

The size of the “author-bubbles” indicates the number of this author publications. The lines between authors represent co-authorship on one or more publications. A thesaurus was used to merge authors with different Elsevier profiles.

References

Elsevier Research Intelligence. (2023). *Scopus quick reference guide*.

https://supportcontent.elsevier.com/RightNow%20Next%20Gen/Scopus/Files/Scopus%20Quick%20Reference%20Guide%20WEB_2023.pdf

Van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84 (2), 523–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>

Data

20250605_brassicaceae_scopus_2025.csv

20250605_brassicaceae_thesaurus.txt

20250605_brassicaceae.json